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Learning Augmented Reality (AR) through Interdisciplinary Project-based Learning (IPBL)

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ABSTRACT

Augmented Reality (AR) is a technique that superimposes virtual content on top of physical objects in the video to provide the viewer with additional information. A well-designed AR system enables people to acquire information related to the real scene objects easily, which also makes further interactions with the real environment possible. Project-based learning (PBL) has been recognized as an effective approach to trigger learner's motivation, which can further promote their higher order thinking and acquisition of academia knowledge. PBL thus has been commonly used in advanced courses in engineering departments. However, it is quite challenging for engineering students to develop an AR system that is well-functioned and carefully addresses the demands of target users by using conventional PBL approach. The key issue alarms us is that developing a useful and satisfactory AR system requires interdisciplinary knowledge and skills from the areas of both computer science and design. Therefore, an interdisciplinary PBL (IPBL) has been proposed in this study, in which students from the engineering departments and the design departments are strategically grouped to work collaboratively on a medical training AR project. A wide range of evidence will be collected and analysed, which enables this study to investigate the effect of the IPBL course on the students' learning motivation, learning self-efficacy, creativity, and problem-solving skills that are necessary for innovation and excellence in their future career as professional AR application developers.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Interdisciplinary education, Project-based Learning (PBL), augmented reality (AR)

INTRODUCTION

Augmented Reality (AR) is a technique that superimposes virtual content on top of physical objects in the video to provide the viewer with additional information. Usually, a built-in camera of a mobile device or smart glasses is used to capture the real scene, and the microprocessor of the device processes the input video with computer vision techniques to understand the image content and/or estimate the camera pose. Computer graphics technology is then applied to draw 2D/3D virtual content on the input image plane according to the semantics of the real object and the pose of the camera. A well-designed AR system enables people to acquire additional information related to the real scene objects, which also makes further interactions with the real environment possible. Therefore, there have been a lot of studies applying AR technology in different domains [1], especially in medical training and education [2][3][4].

Project-based learning (PBL) has been widely recognized as an effective approach to immerse the learners into a contextualized and authentic learning setting, thus has been commonly utilized to nurture the learner's creative problem solving capability in dealing with real-world problems [5][6][7]. Enabling the learners to work in designated task groups, PBL has also been suggested to promote the learner's 21st century skills, including higher order thinking, cooperation and collaboration, and communication and presentation skills. That is, PBL has secured its capability to broaden the learner's horizon, deepen their academic knowledge while exploring and

engaging in real-world scenarios. Since PBL has a wide range of irreplaceable advantages, it is common to apply PBL for college students to learn AR system development. Nonetheless, it should be noted that It is quite challenging for engineering students to develop an AR system that is well-functioned and attentively addresses the demands of target users by applying conventional PBL teaching approach. The key issue alarms us is that developing a useful and satisfactory AR system requires interdisciplinary knowledge and a set of skills from the areas of computer science and design, while the expertise of computer science/engineering can help develop a system with adequate functions, the expertise of design can help improve the understanding of target users, better product ergonomics and aesthetics, and even redesign or create the services associated with the products. Therefore, an interdisciplinary PBL (IPBL) has been proposed in this study, in which students from the engineering departments and the design departments are strategically grouped to work collaboratively on an AR project that helps the users learn medical knowledge and skills more effectively.

For college education, courses that require great amounts of hands-on experience extensively adopt PBL to cement students' practical use of knowledge. However, to better prepare students for the future challenges, traditional PBL can be enhanced by specifically integrating 21st century skills, such as higher order thinking, collaboration and communication, and most important of all - interdisciplinary knowledge and skills. To serve this purpose, this study adopts an IPBL approach, which embeds interdisciplinary knowledge of Design and Computer Science in a course that encourages students to accomplish magnificent and practical AR systems. In our IPBL course, we emphasize the training and development of both AR system implementation ability and design thinking skills [8][9]. A real-world issue – the facilitation of medical training – is used to foster creative problem solving skills. Furthermore, the basis of working in designated task groups enable the group members to work cooperatively and collaboratively whilst applying interdisciplinary knowledge and skills in AR system design for facilitating medical training purpose. Thus, it is expected that the students' communication and social skills can also be improved by participating in the IPBL course [10][11].

1 PARTICIPANTS

A total number of 90 participants aged 22-24 years old are recruited from a top tier university in Taiwan. The participants are randomly assigned to either experimental and control groups. In the experimental group, there are 60 undergraduate and graduate students studying in the departments of Computer Science and Information Engineering (CSIE)/Electronic Engineering (EE), or Industrial Design (ID). In the control group, 30 participants are exclusively recruited from the departments of Computer Science and Information Engineering (CSIE) and Electronic Engineering (EE), but without any design majored (ID) students. In total, 30 groups (2-3 participants per group) are formed with distinct interests in the PBL AR course, among them 20 groups are formed in the experimental group with IPBL course, whereas 10 groups are formed in the control group with Non-IPBL course.

2 RESEARCH PROCEDURES

This study adopts a pretest and posttest quasi-experimental design. The research design is illustrated in Fig. 1. The independent variable is instructional strategy, either interdisciplinary PBL (IPBL: the experimental group) or non-interdisciplinary PBL instruction (Non-IPBL: the control group). In order to investigate the effect of the course, a range of evidence will be collected and analysed to evaluate the student's' augmented reality technology knowledge, problem solving, creativity, learning motivation, and collaboration and communication skills. Furthermore, the student's project products will be consensually evaluated by multiple kinds of stakeholders, including the peer students, professionals, teachers, industrial practitioners, and end users.

As shown in Fig. 2, in the experimental group IPBL course, 60 participants are registered as undergraduate and graduate students studying in the departments of Computer Science and Information Engineering (CSIE)/Electronic Engineering (EE), or Industrial Design (ID). Carefully followed the principles of Double Diamond Design Process Model, the initiative of IPBL course is to promote the learner's interdisciplinary knowledge and skills [12]. The purpose of mixing students of different majors is to facilitate their practice of interdisciplinary knowledge and skills in product design and implementation. As discussed, the expertise of computer science/engineering (students with CSIE and EE majors) can help develop a system with adequate functions, the expertise of design (students with ID major) can help improve the understanding of target users, better product ergonomics and aesthetics, and even redesign/create the services associated with the products. Compared with the lectures delivered in IPBL course, the students in control group (Non-IPBL course) receive lectures with the same teaching materials, however, they are assigned to work with students of similar majors, that is, all members will be recruited exclusively from the departments of Computer Science and Information Engineering (CSIE) and Electronic Engineering (EE). The course is delivered by three professors with diverse professional backgrounds. One professor's background covers the disciplines of industrial design, information science, and psychology; one professor's professional background includes computer science and information engineering; whereas one professor's professional background consists of creativity and imagination education, educational psychology, guidance and counselling, and educational policy analysis.

Fig. 1 Research design

Fig. 2 Course Design of PBL and IPBL

Mainly inspired by Design Thinking approach [12], the 18-week IPBL course is delivered in four phases. The first phase is “discover”: the students are encouraged to discover the real-world issues of their interests and are required to use their empathy to develop a deep understanding of the challenge they are encountering. The second phase is “define”: the students are required to clearly articulate the specific problem they would like to solve through the use of knowledge and skills acquired throughout the course. The third phase is “develop”: the most important task the students need to accomplish is to brainstorm the potential solutions for dealing with the specific problem articulated in the second phase. Since the students of the experimental IPBL group come from diverse backgrounds, it usually takes a longer period of time in the ideation phase. Not only coming up with as many as creative solutions as possible, the students need to repeatedly ask themselves “what do we exactly want to develop?” It is in an essence for the members to select some particular solutions that are agreed to have appropriateness and feasibility. Later one, the students are encouraged to design a prototype (or a series of prototypes) to test the agreed solutions. Before entering the “develop” phase, a card deck named “Design with Intent (Dwl) toolkit [13]” is utilized in the IPBL course to stimulate more and better ideas. The Dwl toolkit provides real world examples of behaviour design which are drawn from many different disciplinary knowledge related to behaviour change. It is useful in moderating the disciplinary differences in the ideation process. The final phase of the IPBL course is “deliver”, the products developed by each group will be presented to potential users through iterative process, in which a range of stakeholders will be invited to ensure their feasibility, creativity, and usefulness of the products.

3 DATA ANALYSES

A mixed methods approach will be used to investigate the effectiveness of the proposed IPBL and PBL course. In the quantitative part, the new version of Chinese Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT) and the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) will be used for the Pretest and Posttest. SPSS statistical analysis software will be employed to analyze the quantitative data collected throughout the study. Firstly, descriptive statistics will be used to describe general results, including the means, standard deviations, and adjusted means, of the tests

between the experimental group and the control group. Secondly, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) will be used to compare the final results of the two groups after the completion of the course, with pretest scores as covariates to eliminate the effect of any existing pretest differences on the results.

In the qualitative part of the study, feedback forms with a range of open-ended questions will be delivered to the participants of the experimental and control groups respectively, while the first feedback form will be collected in the midterm, the second feedback form will be collected after the completion of the course. Several kinds of questions will be asked in the feedback form, including the overall feeling towards the newly developed IPBL approach, the effects of the lectures delivered, and the suggestions for future improvement of relevant courses.

Furthermore, since the participants' final products/works will be consensually evaluated by a range of stakeholders (including the peer students, professionals, teachers, industrial practitioners, and end users), the participants' AR knowledge and skills, problem-solving skills, and communication and collaboration skills can be evaluated in a more comprehensive way.

4 DISCUSSION

A range of evidence will be collected and analysed to evaluate the effectiveness of the courses delivered to the two groups. The quantitative data includes the Pretest and Posttest results of the TTCT and MSLQ, whereas the qualitative data covers the participants' feedbacks towards the intervention of the course design (please see data analysis section for further details). Furthermore, the consensus evaluation on the participant's final products/works enables the study to explore the effect of the IPBL on student's AR knowledge and skills, problem-solving skills, and communication and collaboration skills. With the computation of the statistics results, the comparison of the Pretest and Posttest results between the IPBL and Non-IPBL groups can be made to test the underlying assumptions proposed by the study. Additionally, the complementary qualitative feedbacks collected in the midterm and endterm periods can be used to triangulate the findings.

1) Given that the same teaching materials and lectures will be delivered to both IPBL and Non-IPBL groups, the contrast between pretest and posttest found in the two groups can help identify the content validity of teaching material and the lectures.

2) Although different teaching strategies are delivered to the experimental and control groups, students of both groups will attend the lectures concerning AR system development and the application of computer science and design knowledge. It is expected that the content knowledge of the specific domains of computer science and design will be improved among the participants of both the IPBL and Non-IPBL groups.

3) Since the two groups adopted different teaching strategies, the contrast can be made by comparing the results of the two groups, which can be used to examine whether IPBL can better help students improve their augmented reality technology knowledge, problem solving, creative thinking, learning motivation, and collaboration and communication skills.

4) The initiative of IPBL course can be regarded as one of the frontiers in engineering education in Taiwan, it is expected that the experience of interdisciplinary learning and group working can help trigger the students' learning motivation, improve their

academic performance, collaboration and communication skills, and their so-called 21st century essential high order thinking skills. We earnestly hope that the initiative of IPBL course, delivered through an intriguing and inspiring teaching strategy, can make contribution in engineering education and be extensively applied to ignite the learners' passion and interests in engineering study and better their future career development.

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